

ORIGINAL ARTICLE **OPEN ACCESS**

The Effects of Mobile, Gamified, and Paper Flashcards on Vocabulary and Collocation Learning in Young Language Learners

Ali Soyoo¹ | Barry Lee Reynolds^{2,3} | Ehsan Rassaei⁴ | Boris Vazquez-Calvo⁵

¹Department of English Language Education, The Education University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, SAR, China | ²University of Macau, Faculty of Education, Macau, SAR, China | ³University of Macau, Centre for Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Macau, SAR, China | ⁴Faculty of English Language Studies, Majan University College, Muscat, Oman | ⁵Department of Language Education, University of Seville, Seville, Spain

Correspondence: Barry Lee Reynolds (BarryReynolds@um.edu.mo)

Received: 13 January 2025 | **Revised:** 6 December 2025 | **Accepted:** 15 December 2025

Keywords: flashcards | gamified apps | mobile-assisted vocabulary learning | productive collocation | vocabulary knowledge |

کلیدواژه‌ها: یادگیری واژگان با کمک تلفن همراه، فلش کارت‌ها، دانش واژگانی، هم‌آیندی تولیدی، اپلیکیشن موبایل با قابلیت بازی

ABSTRACT

This study examined English vocabulary learning by using three types of flashcards: paper flashcards, non-gamified mobile application (app) flashcards (i.e., digital flashcards), and gamified mobile app flashcards (i.e., gamified flashcards) in a privately owned language institute in Iran. Employing a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, we quantitatively and qualitatively assessed the impacts of mobile-based flashcards in comparison to paper flashcards on Iranian English as a foreign language (EFL) students' vocabulary and collocation learning. A total of 98 Iranian students, aged 9 to 11, studying EFL in a language institute were selected to participate. The participants were divided into three groups: a paper flashcard group, a digital flashcard group, and a gamified flashcard group. To evaluate their learning, participants' productive collocation knowledge and receptive vocabulary knowledge were quantitatively assessed using a vocabulary and collocation knowledge test. While all groups showed gains in second language vocabulary knowledge, the results revealed that the gamified flashcard group achieved significantly greater gains compared to the digital and paper flashcard groups. Additionally, qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews to explore students' attitudes toward mobile-based flashcards in comparison to paper flashcards. The interview transcripts were analyzed using inductive thematic analysis, revealing three key themes: (1) the vocabulary learning benefits of flashcards, (2) the affective aspect of flashcards, and (3) the challenges associated with using flashcards. The findings offer valuable insights for game designers, language teachers, and parents on when and how to utilize different types of flashcards for vocabulary and collocation learning, considering both their learning benefits and potential challenges.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *International Journal of Applied Linguistics* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

چکیده

این مطالعه یادگیری واژگان زبان انگلیسی در یک مؤسسه خصوصی آموزش زبان در ایران را از طریق سه نوع فلش کارت: فلش کارت‌های کاغذی، فلش کارت‌های مبتنی بر اپلیکیشن موبایلی غیربازی (یعنی فلش کارت‌های دیجیتال) و فلش کارت‌های مبتنی بر اپلیکیشن موبایلی با قابلیت بازی (یعنی فلش کارت‌های دیجیتال با قابلیت بازی) را بررسی کرد. با بهره‌گیری از طرح آمیخته تبیینی متوالی، اثرات فلش کارت‌های مبتنی بر موبایل در مقایسه با فلش کارت‌های کاغذی در یادگیری واژگان و واژگان همنشین زبان انگلیسی به عنوان زبان خارجی به صورت کمی و کیفی ارزیابی شد. در مجموع، ۸۹ زبان‌آموز ایرانی ۹ تا ۱۱ ساله که در یک مؤسسه زبان به یادگیری زبان انگلیسی در این پژوهش شرکت کردند، شرکت‌کنندگان به سه گروه تقسیم شدند: گروه فلش کارت کاغذی، گروه فلش کارت دیجیتال و گروه فلش کارت با قابلیت بازی. برای ارزیابی یادگیری آنها، دانش واژگان همنشین تولیدی و دانش واژگان دریافتی شرکت‌کنندگان با استفاده از آزمون دانش واژگان و واژگان همنشین به صورت کمی ارزیابی شد. در حالی که همه گروه‌ها در دانش واژگان زبان دوم پیشرفت‌هایی را نشان دادند، نتایج نشان داد که گروه فلش کارت با قابلیت بازی در مقایسه با گروه‌های فلش کارت دیجیتال و کاغذی، پیشرفت قابل توجهی بیشتری داشته است. همچنین، داده‌های کیفی از طریق مصاحبه‌های نیمه‌ساختاریافته گردآوری شد تا نگرش دانش‌آموزان نسبت به فلش کارت‌های مبتنی بر موبایل در مقایسه با فلش کارت‌های کاغذی بررسی شود. متن مصاحبه‌ها با استفاده از تحلیل موضوعی استقرایی مورد تجزیه و تحلیل قرار گرفت و سه درون‌مایه کلیدی آشکار شد: (۱) مزایای یادگیری واژگان با فلش کارت‌ها، (۲) جنبه عاطفی فلش کارت‌ها، و (۳) چالش‌های مرتبط با استفاده از فلش کارت‌ها. این یافته‌ها، ادراک ارزشمندی را برای طراحان بازی، معلمان زبان و والدین در مورد زمان و چگونگی استفاده از انواع مختلف فلش کارت‌ها برای یادگیری واژگان و واژگان همنشین، با در نظر گرفتن مزایای یادگیری و چالش‌های بالقوه آنها، ارائه می‌دهد.

1 | Introduction

The growing popularity of digital mobile technologies, such as tablets and smartphones, has sparked increased interest in how second language (L2) learners acquire language in mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) environments (Kukulka-Hulme et al. 2017; Lin and Lin 2019). In particular, Kukulka-Hulme et al. (2017, 217) emphasize the relevance of MALL, noting that it enables L2 learners to learn on an “ongoing basis, in a range of settings, according to a person’s ability and [in a way that is] adapted to their needs.” For example, location-based vocabulary apps employing GPS offer contextually relevant vocabulary-learning experiences to L2 learners (Godwin-Jones 2011). Beyond these technical features, MALL is increasingly recognized for its pedagogical value, supporting the development of core language skills and subskills, especially vocabulary learning.

Vocabulary learning has consistently emerged as a central theme in MALL research over the past two decades (e.g., Hsu et al. 2013; Lin and Lin 2019; Teymouri 2024; Xodabande et al. 2024; Zakian et al. 2022). Among previous studies on MALL and vocabulary learning, a number of these studies have focused on traditional tools such as SMS (Kennedy and Levy 2008; Lu 2008), flashcards (Li and Hafner 2021; Teymouri 2024; Xodabande and Boroughani 2023; Xodabande and Hashemi 2023; Xodabande et al. 2022; Zarrati et al. 2024), and non-gamified apps (Chen and Chan 2019).

However, the focus of the above-mentioned studies has remained largely on receptive vocabulary knowledge, with limited attention to productive knowledge such as accurate collocation use (e.g., Li and Hafner 2021; Mohammadi et al. 2024). While we acknowledge that recent scholarship has begun to explore dimensions of vocabulary knowledge beyond only size, there is a pressing need for exploring how gamified mobile flashcards can affect the productive collocational knowledge of language learners, particularly in young learners. The majority of the existing literature, even when addressing collocation, has primarily employed non-gamified or general MALL tools and focused on adult language learners. This represents a significant research gap, as gamification offers a powerful, theoretically grounded mechanism (e.g., self-determination theory (SDT)) to enhance

the sustained engagement and motivation necessary for the deep processing required to master complex lexical units like collocations. Thus, to address this critical research gap, the present study examined the effectiveness of three types of flashcards in developing both receptive vocabulary knowledge and productive collocation knowledge among elementary-level learners in Iran. By shifting the central focus from MALL broadly to the pedagogical potential of gamification in mobile flashcards for fostering contextually appropriate usage, this study intends to provide a more comprehensive and sharply focused understanding of how this specific tool can support young learners’ vocabulary and collocation development in more meaningful and communicative ways.

2 | Literature Review

The literature review for this study is organized into two main sections. The first section outlines the theoretical frameworks that inform this study, drawing on prior research in MALL and vocabulary learning. The second section synthesizes the literature on vocabulary and collocation knowledge.

2.1 | Theoretical Frameworks

This study relies on two theories that can explain why gamified, digital, or paper flashcards are more or less successful for vocabulary learning: Dual Coding Theory (DCT) and SDT (Clark and Paivio 1991; Deci and Ryan 2000). The rationale for selecting DCT is that it describes “human behavior and experience in terms of dynamic associative processes operating upon an extensive network of modality-specific verbal and nonverbal (or imagery) representations” (Clark and Paivio 1991, 149). As provided in many empirical studies (e.g., Chen and Hsu 2020; Li and Hafner 2021; Soyoof et al. 2024), DCT has been found to be conducive to learning vocabulary in L2, especially when both visual and auditory information are presented to the learners at the same time. Hence, DCT can explain why only those flashcard types (i.e., gamified and digital flashcards) that received additional input for both vision and hearing outperformed those types

that only engaged the visual input, which is only provided by paper flashcards. We further regarded SDT as the second guiding theory of this study, as it can explain why gamified features can provide additional input for meeting psychological needs for L2 vocabulary acquisition based on previous studies (Chen and Zho 2022; Deci and Ryan 2000; Hwang and Chang 2025). For instance, previous studies by Hwang and Chang (2025) and Chen and Zhao (2022) demonstrated that gamified features like immediate feedback and progress tracking directly satisfy the need for competence, while leaderboards address relatedness, which can foster the sustained engagement necessary for the deeper processing of collocations. Taken together, the above-mentioned theories can explain the differences between the three groups in this study based on the nature of the instruction that they received, and more importantly, these theories were supported by solid empirical and relevant studies.

2.2 | Vocabulary and Collocation Knowledge

According to Nation (2022), vocabulary knowledge includes multiple dimensions, such as receptive and productive aspects, which together offer a comprehensive understanding of learners' lexical competence. Receptive knowledge refers to the ability to understand vocabulary in listening and reading contexts, whereas productive knowledge pertains to the ability to use vocabulary accurately in speaking and writing (Schmitt 2014). These two dimensions are interrelated but not interchangeable (Nation 2022). Students often acquire receptive knowledge earlier and in greater volume than productive knowledge, which demands deeper processing and more frequent retrieval (Laufer et al. 2004; Brown 2011).

While receptive knowledge is commonly emphasized in L2 classrooms and assessments, productive collocational competence is essential for learners aiming to use the language fluently and accurately. In particular, studies undertaken by Lewis (1996) and later by Uchiyama et al. (2021) have demonstrated that collocational knowledge significantly contributes to learners' communicative success, academic writing proficiency, and even oral fluency. Despite its importance, this aspect of vocabulary knowledge is underrepresented in the research, particularly in contexts involving younger learners and mobile-assisted instruction.

It is noteworthy that many studies to date have concentrated on adult learners and have primarily explored vocabulary recognition and recall in response to traditional stimuli. As Nation (2022) and Webb (2005) argue, a learner who knows the meaning of a vocabulary word in isolation may still fail to use it effectively in discourse, particularly in syntactically or semantically complex constructions. The neglect of collocational usage in instructional design limits the development of lexical fluency, a cornerstone of native-like language performance. Thus, there is a growing need to investigate pedagogical tools that promote not only breadth (number of known vocabulary) but also depth (how well vocabulary is understood and used contextually) of vocabulary knowledge (Schmitt 2014; Webb 2005). One potential solution to improve students' vocabulary and collocation knowledge is the use of flashcards.

2.3 | L2 Vocabulary and Collocation Development Through Different Types of Flashcards

Flashcards are regarded as one of the oldest and most popular tools for improving L2 vocabulary and collocation knowledge (Honarзад and Soyooф 2023, 2020; Kaitsu and Nakata 2025; Lin and Lin 2019; Teymouri 2024; Xodabande et al. 2024; Zakian et al. 2022). Flashcards are commonly used for their simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and alignment with spaced repetition principles (Li and Hafner 2021; Teymouri 2024). They allow learners to focus on discrete vocabulary items, engage in deliberate practice, and self-regulate their learning. As Schmitt (2010, 2014) notes, flashcards align well with the demands of intentional vocabulary learning, which contrasts with incidental vocabulary acquisition that occurs through exposure to authentic language use.

Among different types of flashcards, both paper-based and digital ones remain one of the most widely used methods to support vocabulary and collocation acquisition. Research has shown that flashcards effectively promote the recognition of form-meaning connections (Chen and Chan 2019; Li and Hafner 2021; Nakata 2020; Reynolds and Shih 2019; Teymouri 2024). In particular, studies involving young learners in Macao and Indonesia have found that flashcard use improves receptive vocabulary retention and may foster productive language skills such as speaking and writing (Chen and Chan 2019; Kusumawardhani 2020; Ngarofah and Sumarni 2018). In Iran, Honarзад and Soyooф (2023) reported better receptive vocabulary outcomes among adult learners using digital flashcards compared to paper flashcards, while studies in China (Li and Hafner 2021) and Thailand (Ma and Yodkamlue 2019) further confirmed the advantages of digital flashcards over paper flashcards for receptive vocabulary learning. Learners also expressed preferences for digital platforms due to their interactivity, convenience, and collaborative features (Başođlu and Akdemir 2010; Lei and Reynolds 2022; Zhonggen 2018; Teymouri 2024).

It is important to consider that many recent studies (e.g., Dehghanzadeh et al. 2020; Honarзад and Soyooф 2020; Kaitsu and Nakata 2025; Qiao et al. 2025) indicated that gamified flashcards can be even more effective than both paper and digital flashcards for L2 vocabulary and collocation knowledge. However, the results of previous studies offered mixed results about the effectiveness of gamified MALL tools for vocabulary learning, which could be due to the nature of apps, languages, or individual differences of participants (Honarзад and Soyooф 2020; Dehghanzadeh et al. 2020; Rachels and Rockinson-Szapkiw 2018). According to Dehghanzadeh et al. (2020) and Kaitsu and Nakata (2025), these inconsistencies could result from individual elements adopted in the given game, such as elements related to rewards in terms of points, which could lead to competitiveness, while other elements related to collaboration could lead to cooperative behavior. Moreover, the nature of the adopted gamification platform itself, whether it is competitive or cooperative, could have a substantial effect on its success with different personalities. On the other hand, the success of gamification in delivering its benefits could also be dependent on appropriate adoption. For example, while some students could perform best in competitive environments, some could suffer from stress, thereby preventing any acquisition of information during the

process. In particular, Rachels and Rockinson-Szapkiw (2018) found that Duolingo was not significantly more effective than traditional instruction for Spanish vocabulary and grammar. In another study, Honarzad and Soyooof (2020) found that gamified vocabulary learning apps are significantly more effective than non-gamified apps for L2 vocabulary learning. Dindar et al. (2021) further demonstrated that cooperative and competitive designs within gamified apps led to deeper vocabulary learning. The effectiveness of gamified apps compared to non-gamified apps for L2 vocabulary learning was supported by review studies (Kaitsu and Nakata 2025; Dehghanzadeh et al. 2020). For example, Kaitsu and Nakata (2025) examined six digital flashcards and found them, especially gamified apps, facilitative for vocabulary learning due to offering various levels of support, such as custom flashcard creation, multilingual support, and feedback features. Furthermore, both Hwang and Chang (2025) and Qiao et al. (2025) reported that gamified apps can enhance the motivation and sustained engagement of students in vocabulary learning.

Taken together, the literature (e.g., Chen and Hsu 2020; Dehghanzadeh et al. 2020; Qiao et al. 2025) indicates that gamified flashcards with elements such as leaderboards, badges, points, timers, and interactive feedback into vocabulary learning can be facilitative for L2 vocabulary and collocation knowledge. These features have been shown to increase students' motivation and engagement while enhancing vocabulary and collocation retention (Chen and Hsu 2020; Dehghanzadeh et al. 2020; Hwang and Chang 2025; Kingsley et al. 2018; Sun and Hsieh 2018).

However, the focus of the above-mentioned studies has remained largely on receptive vocabulary knowledge, with limited attention to productive skills such as accurate collocation use (e.g., Li and Hafner 2021; Mohammadi et al. 2024). More importantly, the participants of studies that focused on students' collocation knowledge were adult language learners, with very limited studies on young students in the literature. This represents a key gap in the field. To address this gap, the current study examines the effectiveness of three types of flashcards—traditional paper flashcards, digital flashcards using DuoCards, and gamified flashcards using Cram—in developing both receptive vocabulary knowledge and productive collocation knowledge among elementary-level learners in Iran. By shifting the focus from simple vocabulary recognition to contextually appropriate usage, this study intends to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how flashcard-based MALL tools, particularly gamified ones, can support young learners' vocabulary and collocation development in more meaningful and communicative ways. Drawing on the aforementioned research gap, this study intends to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the comparative effectiveness of gamified, digital, and paper flashcards on Iranian EFL learners' acquisition of receptive vocabulary knowledge and productive collocation knowledge?
2. What are the attitudes of Iranian EFL students toward the three types of flashcards as methods for vocabulary learning?

3 | Methods

3.1 | Research Design

This study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design (Creswell 2014). In the quantitative phase, students' vocabulary and collocation knowledge were assessed through pre- and post-tests to measure learning gains across the three flashcard groups. In the qualitative phase, students' attitudes toward mobile-based and paper flashcards were examined through semi-structured interviews. The qualitative data helped interpret and contextualize the quantitative results, offering deeper insight into learners' experiences, preferences, and motivation across flashcard formats.

3.2 | Participants

Ninety-eight Iranian learners (73 females, 25 males), aged 9–11, participated in the study. They were elementary-level English learners from a private language institute in Tehran, most of whom attended bilingual primary schools. The institute prepares learners for migration to English-speaking countries, particularly transitions to secondary school in Australia and New Zealand. This migration-oriented context requires learners to acquire academic vocabulary and collocations (e.g., *publish findings*, *conduct research*) to support receptive and productive use at or above the A2 level.

All participants were native Persian speakers with A2 proficiency according to the CEFR, verified through the vocabulary section of the Quick Placement Test (QPT) for Offshore Testing (UCLES 2001), which served as the homogeneity measure. Participants submitted assent and consent forms and were randomly assigned, using cluster random sampling (Dörnyei 2007), to one of three groups: a control group ($N = 32$), a digital flashcard group ($N = 33$), and a gamified flashcard group ($N = 33$). The QPT (UCLES 2001), a reliable vocabulary assessment tool (Honarzad and Soyooof 2020, 2023), was administered before the intervention. A one-way ANOVA confirmed no significant differences in vocabulary knowledge among the three groups prior to treatment (Table 1 in Appendix D).

3.3 | Target Vocabulary and Collocations

The target vocabulary was selected from Form A of the Updated Vocabulary Levels Test (UVLT) at the 3000-word level (Webb et al. 2017), which contains 60 items (see Appendix A). This level bridges high- and mid-frequency vocabulary and is important for elementary learners' comprehension and expression (van Zeeland and Schmitt 2013; Webb et al. 2017). In the UVLT, students answer 10 items, each consisting of a definition with six options. The test assesses knowledge of the 2001–3000 most frequent words, making it suitable for evaluating foundational vocabulary.

In a pilot study at another private language institute in Tehran, 90 elementary-level students completed the test, and results showed that most target words were unfamiliar, confirming

its suitability for measuring learning. The UVLT demonstrates strong reliability, with a KR-21 coefficient of 0.81 (Abu-Bader 2021) and a Pearson reliability of 0.96 based on Rasch analysis (Webb et al. 2017). Construct validity was also established by Webb et al. (2017). Demographic information for pilot participants (52 females, 38 males, aged 9–12) and their QPT proficiency levels is provided in Appendix A.

3.4 | Quasi-Experimental Procedures

The study was conducted in English classes at a private language institute and employed three flashcard approaches: (1) a gamified mobile app (*Cram*), (2) a digital flashcard app (*DuoCards*), and (3) traditional paper flashcards. All materials covered 60 target vocabulary items prepared under the guidance of an English teacher. This section outlines the features of each method and the learning procedures for each group; the teacher oversaw all sessions to minimize intervening variables (see Table 2 in Appendix D). Each group was taught in a separate classroom to prevent cross-group influence.

A randomized block design was used to track changes in the two experimental groups, helping control variation and clarify the effects of digital and gamified tools (Wit and McClure 2004). Each group received 60 minutes of instruction per day for four days, learning 15 words per session. This schedule is appropriate for young Iranian learners aged 9–11, who face specific challenges when acquiring English vocabulary as native Persian speakers. Focused practice time supported comprehension, retention, and academic progress in English-medium contexts.

Following the intervention, participants completed the post-test on day 7 and interviews on day 14. They were then encouraged to continue practicing the target vocabulary at home, using the method corresponding to their assigned group: gamified, digital, or paper flashcards.

3.5 | Student Flashcard Use

In the experimental groups, the learning procedures followed four structured stages under the supervision of an English teacher to ensure consistency across groups and reduce potential intervening variables (Dörnyei 2007). The gamified app incorporated points, a timer, immediate feedback, leaderboards, achievement badges, and rewards to support motivation and engagement (Dehghanzadeh et al. 2021). Points were awarded for correct answers and active study, with immediate feedback provided after each response. A countdown timer added urgency during practice sessions. Leaderboards fostered competition, while badges recognized mastery or study streaks. Rewards, such as unlocked features or streak bonuses, reinforced continued learning. Together, these features support learners' psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness in receptive vocabulary learning and productive collocational use (Deci and Ryan 2000; Dehghanzadeh et al. 2021).

Figures 1–3 show the learning stages for the digital, gamified, and paper flashcard groups, respectively, illustrating how each method supports vocabulary acquisition (Li and Hafner 2021).

Additional procedural details are provided in Figure 4 and Appendix E.

3.6 | Data Collection Instruments

3.6.1 | Vocabulary and Collocation Knowledge (Pre- and Post-Testing)

To assess participants' vocabulary and collocation knowledge, a pre-test was administered during the orientation stage and an identical post-test after the intervention (Figure 4). Both tests included two sections: receptive vocabulary and productive collocation knowledge (Appendix B). Instructions were provided in English and Persian. The receptive section assessed the 3000-word level of the UVLT (Webb et al. 2017) and consisted of 10 items, each with six distractors.

To measure productive collocation knowledge, we designed a test targeting grammatical and lexical collocations (Bahns 1993) related to the target vocabulary (Appendix B). The grammatical section comprised a 10-item cloze test adapted from Bahns (1993, 1998) and Ha (1988). The lexical section required students to translate 10 Persian sentences into English using the target collocations; no points were awarded if the collocation was missing. Additional explanations were provided without hints. All items were based on collocations listed in the *Cambridge Dictionary*, ensuring a focus on learners' ability to use both grammatical and lexical collocations in context (Li and Hafner 2021).

Reliability for the pre- and post-tests was calculated in SPSS 20 and was high across all groups (Cronbach's alpha = 0.73, 0.80, 0.82). Cronbach's alpha was used to assess overtime reliability (Everitt and Skrondal 2010; Lindstrom 2010). Construct validity was confirmed by three experts with extensive experience in CALL and L2 vocabulary research; following Davis's (1992) scale, they reached 96% agreement. Remaining discrepancies were resolved through discussion and iterative revisions.

3.6.2 | Semi-Structured Interviews

One week after the post-test (Figure 4), we used purposive sampling to select interview participants—nine students across the three groups representing high, medium, and low performers (Merriam and Tisdell 2015; Tashakkori and Teddlie 2003). The semi-structured interviews aimed to explore the benefits and concerns associated with each flashcard type. Interview questions are provided in Appendix C.

Four experts in CALL and L2 vocabulary reviewed the interview questions to ensure validity, resolving issues through discussion. For convenience, students chose the interview time and location. Interviews were conducted in Persian, and both transcripts and questions were translated into English by the authors. Persian examples were included during the interviews to ensure comprehension and are shown in Appendix C.

Translations were reviewed and back-translated by four English–Persian translators, who achieved 98% agreement; discrepancies

FIGURE 1 | Screenshots of the DuoCards app. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

were resolved through discussion. The interview data were then coded by four CALL experts, yielding an inter-coder reliability of 92% and a Cohen's kappa of 0.865, indicating strong agreement (Landis and Koch 1977).

3.7 | Data Analysis

We scored participants' responses to the pre- and post-tests to measure changes in vocabulary and collocation knowledge. Participants earned 1 point for each of the 30 items assessing receptive vocabulary knowledge and 1.5 points for each of the 20 items assessing productive collocation knowledge. We allocated a higher weight of score for productive collocation knowledge (i.e., 1.5 points for each item) as it is more challenging compared to receptive vocabulary knowledge.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, repeated measures ANOVA, and the Tukey post hoc test. For the qualitative data, interview transcripts underwent thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns. Further details regarding both types of analyses are given in the results section.

4 | Results

4.1 | Vocabulary and Collocation Knowledge

Prior to conducting statistical analyses, we checked the preliminary data to ensure there were no violations of assumptions related to normality, linearity, homogeneity of variances, and regression slopes. The Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that the

Stage 1

Stage 2

Stage 3

Stage 4

FIGURE 2 | Screenshots of the *Cram* app. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 3 | Sample of Paper Flashcards.

significance values (p) for the paper flashcard, digital flashcard mobile app, and gamified flashcard mobile app groups were 0.07, 0.24, and 0.15, respectively, all above the 0.05 threshold. Thus, the data were normally distributed, allowing for the use of parametric tests.

The first research aim of this study was to evaluate the differences in vocabulary and collocation knowledge across the three groups by comparing pre-test and post-test scores. As shown in Table 3 in Appendix D, the One-way ANOVA results revealed that post-test scores were higher than pre-test scores for all groups. In the paper flashcard group, participants' post-test scores ($M = 39.12$, $SD = 3.31$) were significantly higher than their pre-test scores ($M = 6.90$, $SD = 1.14$), with a medium effect size ($d = 0.97$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, in the digital flashcard app group, post-test scores ($M = 46.75$, $SD = 3.57$) were significantly higher than the pre-test scores ($M = 6.70$, $SD = 1.12$), with a medium effect size ($d = 0.92$, $p < 0.001$). The gamified flashcard group also showed significant

gains, with post-test scores ($M = 54.12$, $SD = 3.75$) significantly higher than pre-test scores ($M = 6.80$, $SD = 1.05$) and a medium effect size ($d = 0.92$, $p < 0.001$).

The mean score increases were most notable in the gamified flashcard group (mean improvement of 47.32 points), followed by the digital flashcard mobile app group (mean improvement of 40.05 points) and the paper flashcard group (mean improvement of 32.21 points). However, the paper flashcard group showed a slightly higher effect size ($d = 0.97$) than the gamified and digital flashcard groups ($d = 0.92$), indicating a greater magnitude of difference within that group.

As indicated in Table 4 in Appendix D, the one-way ANOVA results for the post-test scores show a significant difference among the three groups ($F_{(2,95)} = 144.25$, $p < 0.001$), with a medium effect size ($d = 0.75$). No significant difference was found among the groups in the pre-test ($F_{(2,95)} = 2.18$, $p = 0.80$).

FIGURE 4 | Procedures for the Three Groups. [Color figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

To further examine these post-test score differences, we conducted a Tukey post hoc test. As shown in Table 5 in Appendix D, the Tukey HSD test confirmed significant differences between the paper flashcard ($M = 39.12$, $SD = 3.31$) and both the digital flashcard ($M = 46.75$, $SD = 3.57$) and gamified flashcard groups ($M = 54.12$, $SD = 3.75$).

4.1.1 | Vocabulary and Collocation Learning Comparisons

This section further addresses the first research question. To investigate, mean gain scores from the pre-test and post-test for the three groups were compared using repeated measures ANOVA (Tables 6 and 7 in Appendix D). The analysis revealed a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores across the three groups ($F_{(1,5)} = 4.03$, $p = 0.00$) with a medium effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.95$).

A post hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni correction indicated significant gains in both receptive and productive scores between the pre- and post-tests for each group. Specifically, the gamified flashcard, digital flashcard, and paper flashcard groups showed mean receptive knowledge increases of 26.01, 22.03, and 17.72, respectively. For productive knowledge, the gains for the gamified, digital, and paper flashcard groups were 21.31,

18.02, and 14.49, respectively. Additionally, there was a significant difference in both receptive and productive knowledge across the three groups ($p < 0.05$), again with a medium effect size ($\eta^2 = 0.95$).

4.2 | Student Attitudes Toward Vocabulary Learning Using Different Flashcard Types

To address the second research question, we conducted a thematic analysis of the qualitative data. Thematic analysis, as defined by Braun and Clarke (2006), involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data. Following the six-step process outlined by Braun et al. (2019), we (1) familiarized ourselves with the data, (2) generated initial codes, (3) constructed themes, (4) reviewed the identified themes, (5) defined the final themes for this study, and (6) compiled the report.

Three main themes emerged from the analysis: benefits of flashcards for vocabulary learning, affective responses to flashcards, and challenges associated with using flashcards. Table 8 in Appendix D provides a detailed breakdown of the coding process, including examples. The following sections explore students' experiences and perceptions related to each type of flashcard.

4.2.1 | Vocabulary Learning Benefits of Flashcards

Flashcards are widely regarded as effective tools for vocabulary learning, with each type offering unique advantages suited to different learning styles. Participants identified specific benefits associated with each flashcard format, as summarized in Table 9 in Appendix D.

4.2.2 | Affective Aspects of Flashcards

Emotional engagement is crucial in the learning process. While traditional methods may lose appeal over time, digital flashcards, particularly those with gamified elements, bring renewed energy to vocabulary learning. Summaries of participants' attitudes toward the affective aspects of each flashcard type are presented in Table 10 in Appendix D.

4.2.3 | Challenges Associated With Using Flashcards

Each type of flashcard poses distinct challenges. Paper flashcards may lack convenience, while digital flashcards can be limited by access issues. Gamified flashcards, in particular, may create a mismatch between student enthusiasm and parental concerns. Summaries of these challenges, based on participant feedback, are provided in Table 11 in Appendix D.

4.2.4 | Summary of Challenges in Using Different Flashcard Types

According to participant feedback presented in Tables 9, 10, and 11 in Appendix D, flashcards are effective tools for vocabulary learning, with each format catering to different learning styles with distinct benefits and challenges. Paper flashcards offer a tactile, straightforward learning approach that enhances memorization. Digital flashcards combine traditional learning with technology, facilitating retention and allowing students to review mistakes. Gamified flashcards add an engaging element to the learning experience by incorporating playful features that boost engagement.

However, each flashcard type also presents unique challenges. Paper flashcards lack portability, digital flashcards can lead to concerns about screen time, and gamified flashcards sometimes face parental skepticism over potential distractions. From an emotional perspective, traditional flashcards can become monotonous, whereas digital and gamified formats help sustain interest, with the latter blending learning and entertainment. Ultimately, format choice should consider individual needs, preferences, and external factors, such as parental concerns.

Participant feedback clearly indicates a relationship between flashcard use and vocabulary learning. First, digital flashcards, with their multimedia features, align well with DCT by presenting vocabulary alongside visual images and audio cues. This dual modality aids retention and is one reason learners may prefer digital over paper flashcards, as highlighted by Li and Hafner (2021). Second, gamified flashcards utilize DCT principles by

integrating visual gameplay with auditory feedback or cues, engaging learners through play and challenge (Chen and Hsu 2020). Third, while traditional paper flashcards offer a tactile experience, they generally lack visual and auditory elements. However, students who vocalize vocabulary while using paper flashcards may introduce an auditory component, albeit less consistently than digital cards.

Overall, qualitative data from semi-structured interviews support the quantitative findings that different flashcard types aid L2 vocabulary learning. Specifically, qualitative insights align with quantitative data on the effectiveness of gamified, digital, and paper flashcards for learning both vocabulary and collocations in an L2. Participants provided specific reasons why each format fosters vocabulary and collocation learning, expressing positive attitudes toward gamified, digital, and paper flashcards, respectively. In summary, these findings contextualize flashcard formats within DCT. The inherent visual and auditory elements of digital and gamified flashcards offer an advantage in vocabulary learning, suggesting that format selection should consider not only individual learning preferences but also the cognitive benefits of multimodal input, as proposed by dual coding theory.

5 | Discussion

This study highlights the different effectiveness of mobile-based flashcards, both digital and gamified, and traditional paper flashcards in L2 vocabulary acquisition, interpreted through the lenses of DCT and SDT. These two theoretical frameworks adequately explain the superior performance observed among students using mobile tools, particularly gamified applications, in fostering both receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge.

First, DCT explains the advantage of mobile flashcards over paper-based tools by emphasizing the cognitive benefits of multisensory learning (e.g., text, images, and audio), which enhance memory retention (Paivio 1986). The role of DCT in memory retention was further supported by empirical studies in the literature. For example, Kaitsu and Nakata (2025) reported that auditory reinforcement in digital flashcards improved recall accuracy compared to traditional methods. Similarly, Lin and Lin (2019) highlighted that multisensory input facilitates faster and more robust lexical processing. In contrast, paper flashcards, limited primarily to visual input, lack the auditory and interactive components essential for deep encoding (Li and Hafner 2021; Xodabande et al. 2024). This aligns with the current study's findings, where students using digital and gamified flashcards outperformed those using paper-based tools in receptive vocabulary knowledge gains ($d = 0.95$), thereby reinforcing the explanatory power of DCT in vocabulary acquisition. It is notable that the contribution of digital and gamified flashcards to students' receptive vocabulary learning and collocation knowledge might vary due to different factors, such as the design of these apps (e.g., the features of the application, including their game-designed elements) as well as the individual differences of the targeted participants, such as their age, gender, level of language proficiency, and others. For example, among game design elements, timers and immediate feedback might work better for older learners who can process information more quickly compared to younger students.

Second, SDT explains why the gamified flashcard group outperformed the standard digital group. Gamification elements such as leaderboards, badges, and peer competition are designed to meet learners' basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci and Ryan 1985). These motivational affordances increase learners' engagement and persistence. For example, Qiao et al. (2025) found that gamified vocabulary apps increased time-on-task by demonstrating a direct link between SDT principles and sustained learner involvement. In this study, the gamified group showed the highest gains in productive collocation knowledge ($d = 0.92$), driven by goal-oriented tasks, social interaction, and immediate feedback (Qiao et al. 2025; Soyoof et al. 2025). In contrast, while standard digital flashcards provided multisensory input, they lacked motivational scaffolds, resulting in lower cognitive and behavioral investment (Qiao et al. 2025; Zakian et al. 2022). SDT thus highlights how gamification transforms vocabulary practice into a socially engaging and intrinsically motivating experience, supporting deeper learning outcomes.

Third, the interplay between DCT and SDT provides insights into the observed differences between receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge. While all flashcard types yielded medium to large receptive vocabulary gains ($d = 0.95$), productive collocation knowledge posed greater challenges and required richer contextualized practice. Gamified applications effectively bridged this gap by embedding vocabulary tasks within interactive, motivational contexts (Dehghanzadeh et al. 2021; Ding et al. 2025; Soyoof et al. 2025). Since paper flashcards do not include multisensory stimulation and motivational features, they are not as effective as digital and gamified flashcards for receptive and productive learning of vocabulary and collocation. These findings are in alignment with the studies of Li and Hafner (2021) and Mohammadi et al. (2024), who emphasized that productive vocabulary skills require pedagogical tools that integrate cognitive depth with emotional and social engagement.

Finally, learner perceptions further validate these results. Participants generally preferred mobile tools due to their interactivity, autonomy, and accessibility (Li and Hafner 2021). However, concerns were raised about digital distractions and over-reliance on technology (Tour 2019; Neumann 2016). Conversely, paper flashcards were praised for facilitating focused, distraction-free study sessions, although their lack of portability and interactivity was noted as a limitation. This aligns with prior research advocating for hybrid approaches that combine the benefits of both modalities (Nikoopour and Kazemi 2014; Eutsler and Trotter 2020). Taken together, this study demonstrates that optimal vocabulary learning outcomes are achieved when instructional tools align with both DCT's emphasis on multisensory input and SDT's focus on motivational scaffolding.

6 | Conclusions and Implications

This study aimed to investigate Iranian learners' development of L2 vocabulary knowledge, particularly receptive vocabulary knowledge and productive collocation knowledge, through the use of three types of flashcards: traditional paper-based flashcards, standard digital flashcards, and gamified digital flashcards. The results revealed that all three modalities contributed

positively to vocabulary acquisition, confirming their general effectiveness as vocabulary learning tools. However, clear differences emerged in the extent of their impact, with gamified flashcards producing the highest gains, followed by standard digital flashcards, and then paper flashcards.

This study's primary theoretical contribution lies in showing the nature of the interactivity and the synergies DCT and SDT might have in MALL-based vocabulary acquisition. This research provides evidence that a multisensory design (DCT), particularly one combining text and meaningful pictures with audio, creates the required cognitive scaffolding for processing receptive vocabulary and ultimately remembering it. This cognitive scaffold is then powerfully extended by gamified elements that satisfy SDT's basic needs: autonomy (customizable review schedules, for instance), competence (level advancement with mastery criteria), and relatedness (e.g., cooperative challenges or peer-feedback capabilities). This interaction suggests that optimal instruction for vocabulary and collocation learning must be both cognitively rich and motivationally savvy. The study shows that learners need to apply DCT's cognitive principles (multisensory input: text + image + audio) in alignment with SDT's motivational principles (autonomy, competence, and relatedness) for vocabulary acquisition. An app should have personalized goal trackers where users can set and record their vocabulary goals, alongside challenges that assess mastery and opportunities to give feedback to their peers. It would be valuable if teachers bridged digital tools and the classroom by embedding the app features (such as leaderboards) into classroom activities and received formal training on evaluating apps with DCT and SDT criteria. It would be worthwhile if policymakers supported tools that incorporated DCT and SDT criteria for use in schools. Taken together, the dual application of these theories makes vocabulary and collocation learning cognitively supported and motivationally sustainable so that the gains prove useful in everyday language use rather than merely for passing exams.

7 | Limitations and Suggestions for Future Studies

Several limitations of this study must be acknowledged. First, the absence of a delayed post-test limited the ability to assess learners' long-term retention of vocabulary knowledge. As highlighted by Nakata (2017), repeated retrieval over time is a crucial factor in consolidating vocabulary knowledge and promoting durable retention. Including a follow-up assessment would have provided more comprehensive insight into the lasting effects of each flashcard type. It is important to note that without a delayed post-test, there is no long-term post-observation on vocabulary retention, a critical deficiency for Iran's private institutes that are exam-oriented. Lacking that observation of retention over time, the study cannot claim that app-based learning had an impact on permanent knowledge that could be used in everyday life, outside of short-term exam gains. Second, the integration of target vocabulary into broader learning contexts, such as English texts and discourse, was not systematically incorporated into the experimental design. Although participants were later exposed to English texts containing the target vocabulary during routine lessons, this aspect was not formally analyzed due to constraints imposed by the private language institute. The institution's limited cooperation restricted the scope of instructional

interventions, potentially affecting the ecological validity of the study. Third, ethical considerations also shaped the study design. In particular, the institute's refusal to grant access to additional participant data restricted the depth and breadth of analysis. This included limitations on gathering supplementary demographic or performance data that could have enriched the interpretation of findings. Another limitation of this study is employing the QPT for Offshore Testing (UCLES 2001) as a homogeneity test. It is notable that when this study was accomplished, the QPT for younger students was not developed; we advise future researchers to use this test or other specially designed tests for young students. A further limitation concerns the depth and diversity of the qualitative data. In this study, only nine participants were interviewed, which may not fully capture the range of learner experiences and attitudes toward the different flashcard types. While the interviews provided valuable insights, a larger and more varied qualitative sample, employing methods such as classroom observations, learner diaries, and artifact analysis, could offer a more nuanced understanding of learner engagement and strategy use. Furthermore, the gender imbalance (73 females, 25 males) of the participants is another limitation of this study.

Future research should address these limitations by incorporating delayed post-tests to examine long-term retention and by embedding target vocabulary into authentic, content-rich contexts such as academic texts, dialogues, or project-based learning tasks. For example, digital and gamified flashcards could be evaluated in academic English settings, where multimedia features and real-time feedback may support the acquisition of discipline-specific vocabulary. Additionally, productive collocation learning could be enhanced through tasks that require learners to create original sentences or engage in peer-based storytelling using the target vocabulary, fostering deeper, socially embedded vocabulary use. Researchers are also encouraged to explore hybrid approaches that combine digital tools with collaborative classroom activities. For example, students might co-create multimodal narratives or digital storybooks using vocabulary acquired through gamified apps, reinforcing both form and meaning through creative expression. Furthermore, longitudinal studies with diverse participants could provide insights into how different flashcard types influence not only immediate gains but also sustained vocabulary development over time. Expanding the methodological aspect includes employing varied qualitative approaches and larger sample sizes that can strengthen the evidence base and provide a more holistic view of vocabulary learning processes in different instructional contexts.

Author Contributions

A. S. conceptualized the study, collected the data, and wrote the first draft of the paper. B. L. R. edited the paper, revised the literature review and methodology, revised and validated the quantitative data analysis. E. R. revised the discussion section. B. V.-C. revised the qualitative data analysis and the literature review, and edited the entire paper.

Funding

This study was partially funded by the University of Macau (MYRG-CRG2024-00034-FED).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are not openly available due to reasons of sensitivity and are available from the first author upon reasonable request.

References

- Abrams, S. S., and S. Walsh. 2014. "Gamified Vocabulary: Online Resources and Enriched Language Learning." *Journal of Adolescent and Adult Literacy* 58, no. 1: 49–58. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jaal.315>.
- Abu-Bader, S. H. 2021. *Using Statistical Methods in Social Science Research: With a Complete SPSS Guide*. Oxford University Press.
- Atmaja, A. S. K., and G. Sonia. 2020. "Using Flash Cards To Improve Students' Vocabulary." *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)* 3, no. 2: 283. <https://doi.org/10.22460/project.v3i2.p28.3-289>.
- Bahns, J. 1993. "Lexical Collocations: A Contrastive View." *ELT Journal* 47, no. 1: 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/47.1.56>.
- Başoğlu, E. B., and Ö. Akdemir. 2010. "A Comparison of Undergraduate Students' English Vocabulary Learning: Using Mobile Phones and Flash Cards." *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology* 9, no. 3: 1–7. <http://www.tojet.net/articles/v9i3/931.pdf>.
- Braun, V., and V. Clarke. 2006. "Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology." *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3, no. 2: 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp0630a>.
- Braun, V., V. Clarke, N. Hayfield, G. Terry, and P. Liamputtong. 2019. *Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences*. Springer Nature Group, 843–860. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-2779-6_103-1.
- Brown, D. 2011. "What Aspects of Vocabulary Knowledge Do Textbooks Give Attention to?" *Language Teaching Research* 15, no. 1: 83–97. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168810383345>.
- Chen, H. J. H., and H. L. Hsu. 2020. "The Impact of a Serious Game on Vocabulary and Content Learning." *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 33, no. 7: 811–832. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2019.1593197>.
- Chen, R. W., and K. K. Chan. 2019. "Using Augmented Reality Flashcards to Learn Vocabulary in Early Childhood Education." *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 57, no. 7: 1812–1831. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633119854028>.
- Chen, Y., and S. Zhao. 2022. "Understanding Chinese EFL Learners' Acceptance of Gamified Vocabulary Learning Apps: An Integration of Self-Determination Theory and Technology Acceptance Model." *Sustainability* 14: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141811288>.
- Clark, J. M., and A. Paivio. 1991. "Dual Coding Theory and Education." *Educational Psychology Review* 3, no. 3: 149–210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01320076>.
- Craik, F. I. M., and R. S. Lockhart. 1972. "Levels of Processing: A Framework for Memory Research." *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behavior* 11, no. 6: 671–684. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5371\(72\)80001-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5371(72)80001-X).
- Creswell, J. W. 2014. *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th ed. Sage Publications, Incorporated.
- Dağdeler, K. O., M. Y. Konca, and H. Demiröz. 2020. "The Effect of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) on EFL Learners' Collocation Learning." *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies* 16, no. 1: 489–509. <https://doi.org/10.17263/jlls.712891>.
- Davis, L. L. 1992. "Instrument Review: Getting the Most From a Panel of Experts." *Applied Nursing Research* 5, no. 4: 194–197. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0897-1897\(05\)80008-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0897-1897(05)80008-4).
- Dehghanzadeh, H., H. Fardanesh, J. Hatami, E. Talaei, and O. Noroozi. 2021. "Using Gamification to Support Learning English as a Second

- Language: A Systematic Review.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 34, no. 7: 934–957. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2019.1648298>.
- Dindar, M., L. Ren, and H. Järvenoja. 2021. “An Experimental Study on the Effects of Gamified Cooperation and Competition on English Vocabulary Learning.” *British Journal of Educational Technology* 52, no. 1: 142–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12977>.
- Ding, C., and B. L. Reynolds. 2019. “The Effects of L1 Congruency, L2 Proficiency, and the Collocate-node Relationship on the Processing of L2 English Collocations by L1-Chinese EFL Learners.” *Review of Cognitive Linguistics* 17, no. 2: 331–357. <https://doi.org/10.1075/rcl.00038.din>.
- Ding, C., B. L. Reynolds, and X. V. Ha. 2024. “Learners’ Perceptions of a Collocation Instruction and Practice Component in a Chinese EFL Context.” *The Language Learning Journal* 52, no. 1: 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2022.2098366>.
- Ding, C., B. L. Reynolds, C. Z. Szabo, and G. Boone. 2025. “Assessing English Language Learners’ Collocation Knowledge: A Systematic Review of Receptive and Productive Measurements.” *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching* 63, no. 2: 833–856. <https://doi.org/10.1515/iral-2022-0163>.
- Dizon, G., and D. Tang. 2017. “Comparing the Efficacy of Digital Flashcards Versus Paper Flashcards to Improve Receptive and Productive L2 Vocabulary.” *The EuroCALL Review* 25, no. 1: 3–15. <https://doi.org/10.4995/eurocall.2017.696>.
- Dörnyei, Z. 2007. *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford University Press.
- Eutsler, L., and J. Trotter. 2020. “Print or iPad? Young Learners’s Text Type Shared Reading Preference and Behaviors in Comparison to Parent Predictions and At-Home Practices.” *Literacy Research and Instruction* 59, no. 4: 324–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19388071.2020.1777229>.
- Everitt, B. S., and A. Skrondal. 2010. *The Cambridge Dictionary of Statistics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gee, J. P. 2009. “Deep Learning Properties of Good Digital Games: How Far Can They Go?” In *Serious Games*, edited by U. Ritterfeld, M. Cody, and P. Vorderer, 89–104. Routledge.
- Godwin-Jones, R. 2011. “Emerging Technologies: Mobile Apps for Language Learning.” *Language Learning & Technology* 15, no. 2: 2–11. <http://llt.msu.edu/issues/june2011/emerging.pdf>.
- Ha, M. 1988. “Acquisition of Collocations: Investigation of Relative Difficulty Among Different Types of Collocations.” Unpublished manuscript, University of Hawaii.
- Honarzad, R., and A. Soyoo. 2020. “Vocabulary Learning and Retention: A Comparison Between a Serious Game and Mobile Application.” *International Journal of Pedagogies and Learning* 15, no. 1: 81–100. http://www.adamhousepress.com.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/5_Honarzad_final.pdf.
- Honarzad, R., and A. Soyoo. 2023. “Two Vocabulary Learning Tools Used by Iranian EFL Learners: Physical Flashcards versus a Mobile App.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 24, no. 1: 159–177. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367340741_Two_Vocabulary_Learning_Tools_Used_by_Iranian_EFL_Learners_Physical_Flashcards_versus_a_Mobile_App.
- Hsu, C. K., G. J. Hwang, Y. T. Chang, and C. K. Chang. 2013. “Effects of Video Caption Modes on English Listening Comprehension and Vocabulary Acquisition Using Handheld Devices.” *Journal of Educational Technology and Society* 16, no. 1: 403–414. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jeductechsoci.16.1.403>.
- Hsu, J. Y., and C. Y. Chiu. 2008. “Lexical Collocations and Their Relation to Speaking Proficiency of College EFL Learners in Taiwan.” *Asian EFL Journal* 10, no. 1: 181–204.
- Hwang, G. J., and C. C. Chang. 2025. “A Self-Determination Theory-based Digital Gaming Approach to Enhancing EFL Learners’ Competence in Applying Professional English.” *Educational Technology Research Development* 73: 1205–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-024-10445-y>.
- Jensen, S. H. 2017. “Gaming as an English Language Learning Resource Among Young Learners in Denmark.” *Calico Journal* 34, no. 1: 1–19. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/90014675>.
- Kaitsu, T., and T. Nakata. 2025. “Analysis of Smartphone-Based Flashcard Apps for Second Language Vocabulary Acquisition.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2025.2481396>.
- Kennedy, C., and M. Levy. 2008. “L’italiano al telefonino: Using SMS to Support Beginners’ Language Learning.” *ReCALL* 20, no. 3: 315–330. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344008000530>.
- Kingsley, T. L., and M. M. Grabner-Hagen. 2018. “Vocabulary by Gamification.” *The Reading Teacher* 71, no. 5: 545–555. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1645>.
- Kukulka-Hulme, A., H. Lee, and L. Norris. 2017. “Mobile Learning Revolution: Implications for Language Pedagogy.” In *The Handbook of Technology and Second Language Teaching and Learning*, edited by C. A. Chapelle and S. Sauro, 217–233. Wiley Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118914069.ch15>.
- Kusumawardhani, P. 2020. “The Use of Flashcards for Teaching Writing to English Young Learners (EYL).” *Scope: Journal of English Language Teaching* 4, no. 1: 35–47. <https://doi.org/10.30998/scope.v4i01.4519>.
- Landis, J. R., and G. G. Koch. 1977. “An Application of Hierarchical Kappa-type Statistics in the Assessment of Majority Agreement Among Multiple Observers.” *Biometrics* 33, no. 2: 363–374. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2529786>.
- Laufer, B., C. Elder, K. Hill, and P. Congdon. 2004. “Size and Strength: Do We Need Both to Measure Vocabulary Knowledge?” *Language Testing* 21, no. 2: 202–226. <https://doi.org/10.1191/0265532204lt277oa>.
- Lee, J. S., and N. A. Drajerati. 2019. “Affective Variables and Informal Digital Learning of English: Keys to Willingness to Communicate in a Second Language.” *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology* 35, no. 5: 168–182. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.5177>.
- Lei, Y., and B. L. Reynolds. 2022. “Learning English Vocabulary From Word Cards: A Research Synthesis.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 13: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.984211>.
- Lewis, M. 1996. “Implications of a Lexical View of Language.” In *Challenge and Change in Language Teaching*, edited by D. Willis and J. Willis, 10–16. Oxford.
- Li, Y., and C. A. Hafner. 2021. “Mobile-Assisted Vocabulary Learning: Investigating Receptive and Productive Collocation Knowledge of Chinese EFL Learners.” *ReCALL* 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344021000161>.
- Lin, J. J., and H. Lin. 2019. “Mobile-assisted ESL/EFL Vocabulary Learning: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 32, no. 8: 878–919. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2018.1541359>.
- Lindstrom, D. 2010. *Schaum’s Easy Outline of Statistics, Second Edition (Schaum’s Easy Outlines)*. 2nd ed. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Lu, M. 2008. “Effectiveness of Vocabulary Learning via Mobile Phone.” *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 24, no. 6: 515–525. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2008.00289.x>.
- Ma, X., and B. Yodkamlue. 2019. “The Effects of Using a Self-Developed Mobile App on Vocabulary Learning and Retention Among EFL Learners.” *PASAA: Journal of Language Teaching and Learning in Thailand* 58: 166–205. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1227379.pdf>.
- Merriam, S. B., and E. J. Tisdell. 2015. *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Mohammadi, M., M. Valizadeh, P. Zohdi Jalal, and I. Xodabande. 2024. “University Students’ Academic Vocabulary Development Through Mobile-Assisted Learning: Exploring the Impacts on Receptive and Productive Knowledge.” *Heliyon* 10: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e28103>.
- Nakata, T. 2017. “Does Repeated Practice Make Perfect? The Effects of Within-Session Repeated Retrieval on Second Language Vocabulary

- Learning.” *Studies in Second Language Acquisition* 39, no. 4: 653–679. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263116000280>.
- Nakata, T. 2020. “Learning Words With Flash Cards and Flashcards.” In *The Routledge Handbook of Vocabulary Studies*, edited by S. Webb, 304–319. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429291586-20>.
- Nation, I. S. 2022. *Learning Vocabulary in Another Language*. 3rd ed. Cambridge University Press.
- Nation, P. 2019. “The Different Aspects of Vocabulary Knowledge.” In *The Routledge Handbook of Vocabulary Studies*, edited by S. Webb, 15–29. Routledge.
- Neumann, M. M. 2016. “Young Learners’s Use of Touch Screen Tablets for Writing and Reading at Home: Relationships With Emergent Literacy.” *Computers & Education* 97: 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2016.02.013>.
- Ngarofah, S., and A. Sumarni. 2018. “Teaching Vocabulary Using Flashcard to Young Learner.” *PROJECT (Professional Journal of English Education)* 1, no. 6: 775–782. <https://doi.org/10.22460/project.v1i6.p775-782>.
- Nguyen, T. M. H., and S. Webb. 2017. “Examining Second Language Receptive Knowledge of Collocation and Factors That Affect Learning.” *Language Teaching Research* 21, no. 3: 298–320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168816639619>.
- Nikoopour, J., and A. Kazemi. 2014. “Vocabulary Learning Through Digitized and Non-Digitized Flashcards Delivery.” *Procedia—Social and Behavioral Sciences* 98: 1366–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.03.554>.
- Panfilova, V., V. Spichak, and A. Zhumakhanova. 2022. “Educational Mobile Games as a Tool for Increasing Vocabulary When Learning a Foreign Language.” *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies (IJWLTT)* 17, no. 1: 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJWLTT.298624>.
- Plonsky, L., and F. L. Oswald. 2014. “How Big Is ‘Big’? Interpreting Effect Sizes in L2 Research.” *Language Learning* 64, no. 4: 878–912. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12079>.
- Qiao, S., S. K. W. Chu, and S. S. S. Yeung. 2025. “Understanding How Gamification of English Morphological Analysis in a Blended Learning Environment Influences Students’ Engagement and Reading Comprehension.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 38, no. 4: 831–864. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2023.2230273>.
- Rachels, J. R., and A. J. Rockinson-Szapkiw. 2018. “The Effects of a Mobile Gamification App on Elementary Students’ Spanish Achievement and Self-Efficacy.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 31, no. 1–2: 72–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2017.1382536>.
- Read, J. 2000. *Assessing Vocabulary*. Cambridge University Press.
- Reinhardt, J. 2019. “Game.” In *Gameful Second and Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*. 77–100. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Reynolds, B. L. 2016. “Action Research: Applying a Bilingual Parallel Corpus Collocational Concordance to Taiwanese Medical School EFL Academic Writing.” *RELJ Journal: A Journal of Language Teaching and Research* 47, no. 2: 213–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688215619518>.
- Reynolds, B. L., and Y. C. Shih. 2019. “The Learning Effects of Student-Constructed Flashcards as Homework for the Adolescent English Language Classroom.” *System* 81: 146–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.01.005>.
- Reynolds, B. L., and M. F. Teng. 2021. “Innovating Teacher Feedback With Writing Activities Aimed at Raising Secondary School Students’ Awareness of Collocation Errors.” *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching* 11, no. 3: 423–444. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2021.11.3.6>.
- Reynolds, B. L., W. H. Wu, and Y. C. Shih. 2020. “Which Elements Matter? Constructing Flashcards for English Vocabulary Growth.” *SAGE Open* 10, no. 2: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020919512>.
- Ryan, R., and E. Deci. 2000. “Self-Determination Theory and the Facilitation of Intrinsic Motivation, Social Development, and Well-being.” *The American Psychologist* 55, no. 1: 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>.
- Sailer, M., J. U. Hense, S. K. Mayr, and H. Mandl. 2017. “How Gamification Motivates: An Experimental Study of the Effects of Specific Game Design Elements on Psychological Need Satisfaction.” *Computers in Human Behavior* 69: 371–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.033>.
- Schmitt, N. 2010. *Researching Vocabulary: A Vocabulary Research Manual*. Palgrave Macmillan. 1057/9780230293977.
- Schmitt, N. 2014. “Size and Depth of Vocabulary Knowledge: What the Research Shows.” *Language Learning* 64, no. 4: 913–951. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12077>.
- Snoder, P., and B. L. Reynolds. 2019. “How Dictogloss Can Facilitate Collocation Learning in ELT.” *ELT Journal* 73, no. 1: 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccy024>.
- Soyoof, A. 2023. “Iranian EFL Students’ Perception of Willingness to Communicate in an Extramural Digital Context.” *Interactive Learning Environments* 31, no. 9: 5922–5939. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2021.2024579>.
- Soyoof, A., B. L. Reynolds, K. K. Chan, W. T. Tseng, and K. McLay. 2025. “Massive Online Multiplayer Games as an Environment for English Learning Among Iranian EFL Students.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 38, no. 1–2: 128–171. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2023.2171065>.
- Soyoof, A., B. L. Reynolds, R. Shadiev, and B. Vazquez-Calvo. 2024. “A Mixed-methods Study of the Incidental Acquisition of Foreign Language Vocabulary and Healthcare Knowledge Through Serious Game Play.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 37, no. 1–2: 27–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2021.2021242>.
- Soyoof, A., B. L. Reynolds, B. Vazquez-Calvo, and K. McLay. 2023. “Informal Digital Learning of English (IDLE): a Scoping Review of What Has Been Done and a Look towards What Is to Come.” *Computer Assisted Language Learning* 36, no. 4: 608–640. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2021.1936562>.
- Sun, J. C.-Y., and P.-H. Hsieh. 2018. “Application of a Gamified Interactive Response System to Enhance the Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation, Student Engagement, and Attention of English Learners.” *Journal of Educational Technology and Society* 21, no. 3: 104–116.
- Sundqvist, P. 2019. “Commercial-off-the-shelf Games in the Digital Wild and L2 Learner Vocabulary.” *Language Learning and Technology* 23, no. 1: 87–113.
- Tashakkori, A., and C. Teddlie. 2003. “Issues and Dilemmas in Teaching Research Methods Courses in Social and Behavioural Sciences: US Perspective.” *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* 6, no. 1: 61–77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645570305055>.
- Teng, F. 2018. “Incidental Vocabulary Acquisition From Reading-only and Reading-while-listening: A Multi-dimensional Approach.” *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching* 12, no. 3: 274–288. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2016.1203328>.
- Teymouri, R. 2024. “Recent Developments in Mobile-assisted Vocabulary Learning: A Mini Review of Published Studies Focusing on Digital Flashcards.” *Frontiers in Education* 9: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1496578>.
- Tour, E. 2019. “Supporting Primary School Learners’ learning in Digital Spaces at Home: Migrant Parents’ Perspectives and Practices.” *Learners & Society* 33, no. 6: 587–601. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12347>.
- Uchihara, T., M. Eguchi, J. Clenton, K. Kyle, and K. Saito. 2021. “To what Extent Is Collocation Knowledge Associated With Oral Proficiency? A Corpus-Based Approach to Word Association.” *Language and Speech* 65, no. 2: 311–336. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00238309211013865>.
- UCLES (University of Cambridge Local Examinations Syndicate). 2001. *Quick Placement Test*. Oxford University Press.

- Van Zeeland, H., and N. Schmitt. 2013. "Lexical Coverage in L1 and L2 Listening Comprehension: The Same or Different From Reading Comprehension?" *Applied Linguistics* 34, no. 4: 457–479. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/ams074>.
- Waluyo, B., and J. L. Bucol. 2021. "The Impact of Gamified Vocabulary Learning Using Quizlet on Low-proficiency Students." *Computer Assisted Language Learning Electronic Journal* 22, no. 1: 164–185. <http://callej.org/journal/22-1/Waluyo-Bucol2021.pdf>.
- Wang, B. T., C. W. Teng, and H. T. Chen. 2015. "Using iPad to Facilitate English Vocabulary Learning." *International Journal of Information and Education Technology* 5, no. 2: 100–104. <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJNET.2015.V5.484>.
- Webb, S. 2005. "Receptive and Productive Collocation Learning: The Effects of Reading and Writing on Word Knowledge." *Studies in Second Language Acquisition* 27, no. 1: 33–52. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263105050023>.
- Webb, S. 2019. "Incidental Vocabulary Learning." In *The Routledge Handbook of Vocabulary Studies*, edited by S. Webb, 225–239. Routledge.
- Webb, S., Y. Sasao, and O. Ballance. 2017. "The Updated Vocabulary Levels Test: Developing and Validating Two New Forms of the VLT." *ITL-International Journal of Applied Linguistics* 168, no. 1: 33–69. <https://doi.org/10.1075/itl.168.1.02web>.
- Webb, S. A. 2009. "The Effects of Pre-learning Vocabulary on Reading Comprehension and Writing." *Canadian Modern Language Review* 65, no. 3: 441–470. <https://doi.org/10.3138/cmlr.65.3.441>.
- Wit, E., and J. McClure. 2004. *Statistics for Microarrays: Design, Analysis and Inference*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Xodabande, I., M. R. Atai, and M. R. Hashemi. 2024. "Exploring the Effectiveness of Mobile Assisted Learning With Digital Flashcards in Enhancing Long-Term Retention of Technical Vocabulary Among University Students." *Journal of Computers in Education* 12: 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-024-00347-6>.
- Xodabande, I., and T. Boroughani. 2023. "Mobile-assisted Focus on Forms in English for Academic Purposes Instruction: Investigating the Impacts on Learning Academic Words." *Frontiers in Psychology* 14: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1071555>.
- Xodabande, I., and M. R. Hashemi. 2023. "Learning English With Electronic Textbooks on Mobile Devices: Impacts on University Students' Vocabulary Development." *Education and Information Technologies* 28: 1587–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11230-1>.
- Xodabande, I., Y. Iravi, B. Mansouri, and H. Matinparsa. 2022. "Teaching Academic Words With Digital Flashcards: Investigating the Effectiveness of Mobile-assisted Vocabulary Learning for University Students." *Frontiers in Psychology* 13: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.893821>.
- Zakian, M., I. Xodabande, M. Valizadeh, and M. Yousefvand. 2022. "Out-of-the-classroom Learning of English Vocabulary by EFL Learners: Investigating the Effectiveness of Mobile Assisted Learning With Digital Flashcards." *Asian-Pacific Journal of Second and Foreign Language Education* 7, no. 1: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40862-022-00143-8>.
- Zarrati, Z., M. Zohrabi, H. Abedini, and I. Xodabande. 2024. "Learning Academic Vocabulary With Digital Flashcards: Comparing the Outcomes From Computers and Smartphones." *Social Sciences & Humanities Open* 9: 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.100900>.
- Zhang, X., and B. L. Reynolds. 2023. "A Mixed-Methods Investigation of the Effectiveness and Perceptions of Learning English Collocations Using the Keyword Method and the Rote Learning Method." *Behavioral Sciences* 13, no. 7: 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs13070591>.
- Zhonggen, Y. 2018. "Differences in Serious Game-aided and Traditional English Vocabulary Acquisition." *Computers & Education* 127: 214–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.07.014>.
- Zou, D., Y. Huang, and H. Xie. 2021. "Digital Game-based Vocabulary Learning: Where Are We and Where Are We Going?" *Computer Assisted*

Language Learning 34, no. 5–6: 751–777. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2019.1640745>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting file 1: ijal70095-sup-0001-appendix.docx